

THE EFFECT OF QUALITY CULTURE ON THE QUALITY OF SERVICE AND STUDENT SATISFACTION MEDIATED BY THE QUALITY OF INFRASTRUCTURE AND CORE QUALITY AT TSANAWIYAH MADRASAH UMMUSSHABRI

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine and examine the influence of quality culture, core quality, service quality, satisfaction on infrastructure quality. Then to find out and examine the influence of infrastructure quality on core quality and service quality. Furthermore, to examine the effect of core quality on service quality, the effect of service quality on student satisfaction at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Ummusshabri Kendari. Then examine the mediating role of infrastructure quality on the influence of quality culture on core quality, mediating role of core quality on the influence of infrastructure quality on service quality at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Ummusshabri Kendari. The population in this study were all students at the Madrasah Tsanawiyah level at the Ummusshabri Foundation, Kendari City, totaling 576 students. In this study, three types of research variables will be used, including independent, mediating, and dependent variables. The variables include, the independent variable is quality culture, then the mediating variable is infrastructure quality and core quality, while the dependent variable is service quality and satisfaction. The data collection technique used in this research is first, a survey, conducted by distributing questionnaires to the respondents, namely students of Madrasah Tsanawiyah Kendari Ummusshabri Foundation. Second, observation is a technique of collecting data by making direct observations and noting phenomena that occur at the research location. With observation, the activities of the research object can be directly observed, while to test the pattern of relationships between research variables, descriptive inferential statistics uses the concept of Structural Equation Model (SEM) with Partial Least Square (PLS) program. The results of this study indicate that quality culture, core quality, service quality, satisfaction have a positive and significant effect on infrastructure quality. Infrastructure quality has a positive and significant effect on core quality and service quality, then core quality has a positive and significant effect on service quality, service quality has a positive effect on student satisfaction at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Ummusshabri Kendari. Then the mediating role of infrastructure quality is not able to mediate quality culture on core quality, while core quality is able to mediate on the influence of infrastructure quality on service quality at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Ummusshabri Kendari.

Keywords: *Quality Culture, Service Quality, Satisfaction, Infrastructure Quality and Core Quality.*

INTRODUCTION

Education is one way that can be done to be able to develop human personality and abilities towards a better life. Education takes place without any specific time and space boundaries throughout Ahmed's life (1999). An educational institution is expected to participate in building the nation's intelligence by providing training and teaching to its students to produce quality output. Schools as organizations function to foster creative and innovative human resources in order to meet the demands of an ever-changing era (Anwar (2014).

The demand for the quality of education is getting stronger. The community continues to demand improvement in quality-based education services with very detailed quality criteria. The quality of the process of providing education and the quality of alumni will be a measure of the quality of educational institutions in providing services. Competition in the world of education is now getting tougher. Competition in the concept of curriculum, infrastructure, learning activity programs and the quality of educators and education staff is a measure of whether an educational institution is said to be of good quality or not. Even in international competitions, education is faced with competition for the quality of alumni who are well educated, well skilled and well technological. Graduates of quality educational institutions not only have knowledge of the knowledge and insights learned, but also have adequate skills and personalities.

One way that can be done to overcome the problems of the quality of education above is to implement Total Quality Management (TQM) or integrated quality management in schools. Total quality management is the concept of continuous improvement of product and service quality to achieve maximum customer satisfaction through: focusing on consumer needs, involvement of all employees at every level of the organization, and continuous improvement of the quality of products, services, people, processes. and organizational environment. The implementation of integrated quality management is expected to change the pattern of a centralized approach to become more flexible by giving authority to the school so that it can freely manage the educational process and make decisions related to the survival of the school.

Quality culture aims to form a quality culture in madrasas so that they become organizations that respect quality and make quality an orientation that can be implemented by all components of the madrasa. If this management is established in educational institutions, then the leadership should try to build awareness of its members starting from the leadership itself, teaching staff, education staff, students, and various related elements, such as work units and users of graduates of Mutohar (2013). The perceived service quality from the application of a quality culture and the application of quality management practices is able to provide impetus to create satisfaction. As the findings of Patyal & Koilakunta (2017) which reveal that the perceived service quality will be better when the implementation of quality management practices goes well. Bennett. R, et al. (2003) also revealed that with good service quality, satisfaction will arise because of conformity to individual expectations.

There is also an empirical phenomenon that is also the basis of this research. This study will focus on examining one of the madrasas under the umbrella of the Ummusshabri Kendari foundation, namely Madrasah Tsanawiah, the Ummusshabri Foundation, which was legally established in 2009. Prior to the establishment of the Ummusshabri Foundation in Kendari, institutional activities were running as they should by using the name Pondok Pesantren Ummusshabri. In its activities according to observations made that the application of quality management practices is still not optimal. This is indicated by the still less than optimal commitment to the involvement of the school management in internal and external aspects in carrying out the activities of the learning process. In addition, the application of a sustainable quality culture also needs to be a concern from the Madrasah so that it can create a continuity of service quality that can be provided to its consumers (students) and also the satisfaction that can be felt by every related party.

One of the efforts to improve the quality of education at Madrasah Tsanawiyah carried out by the Ummusshabri foundation can be seen in the formation of a superior class named Ciber (Smart, Intellectual, Talented, Religious) which has been started in 2015. This program is aimed at developing the potential of students to become Humans who believe and fear God Almighty, have good morals, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent and become democratic and responsible citizens. In the process, students who are members of the Ciber program are given complete facilities to support the learning process and are supported by teachers who have competencies that are specially selected to support the development of students' abilities, and are given priority when there are academic or non-academic events. On the other hand, this tends to cause the jealousy of other students who cannot enter the class program. Equitable treatment of students is one of the conditions that need to be considered in providing good service and creating satisfaction from students during the learning process they go through so that they are able to produce graduates who have quality and character.

In addition to this, there is still dissatisfaction from students with the existing learning process which is also one of the benchmarks for the need for improvement in terms of quality management. The involvement of key parties as part of the madrasah management infrastructure needs to also get attention. The need to realize madrasas that prioritize input, process, output, and supervision in improving the quality of madrasas, must continue to be carried out by involving all stakeholders and education implementers so that the quality of madrasas is maintained.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Quality Culture Concept

Quality culture is part of organizational culture. The concept of organizational culture has been widely accepted as a way of understanding human systems. From the perspective of openness, every aspect of organizational culture can be seen as an important environmental condition that affects the system and its subsystems. Berings & Verheschen (2010). defines culture as dynamic and definitive goals and tools (values, ethics, rules, knowledge systems)

developed to achieve group goals. Petruzzellis & Romanazzi (2006) define culture as related to people's understanding of themselves, their world, and the influence on education. Meanwhile, Powell (2011) defines culture as a simple way of saying how an organization expresses itself internally and externally.

Quality culture is a culture in which everyone in the organization is not only a quality controller, but is also responsible for quality. Culture can consist of all the institutionalized ways and implicit ideas, norms, values, and premises that emphasize and influence behavior. According to Ahmed et al. (1999) there are different definitions of culture, but they all refer to a single set, material, or pattern of behavior defined by a group as a standard way of solving problems. Sattler and Sonntag (2018) consider that culture is best understood as a set of shared implicit assumptions that have been accepted and have shaped a person's daily behavior. It is further explained that quality culture is closely related to the well-known concept of organizational culture at three different levels: artifacts, advocated values of an organization and shared basic assumptions (Sattler & Sonntag, 2018).

Quality Management Practice

Quality management practices are managerial actions that refer to quality management activities (Flynn et al., 1994). Quality management can be seen as a management philosophy characterized by principles, practices and techniques emphasizing continuous improvement, increased employee engagement and teamwork, process orientation, competitive benchmarking, committed leadership, and constant measurement of results (Ronnback and Witell, 2008). . Educational institutions are becoming more aware of the importance of quality education (Paquette et al., 2011). Many of them have turned to quality management practices that can solve quality problems and ultimately provide superior organizational performance (Evans, 2010; Lee et al., 2013).

The term quality management practice has been used more widely in the literature than quality management principles because the behavioral characteristics of the practice can be easily measured compared to overly general principles and overly detailed techniques (Sousa and Voss, 2002). Quality management practices include the best strategies adopted and implemented by many organizations around the world to improve quality and performance and increase customer satisfaction (Brah et al., 2002; Dahlgaard-Park, 2011; Flynn et al., 1995; Addis, 2020).

Infrastructure Quality

Infrastructure quality is one component of quality management that shapes quality in an organization by emphasizing aspects of existing human resources and also on the concept of behavior that exists within the organization. Patyal and Koilakunta (2017) define infrastructure quality practices as one of the characteristics of quality management that is oriented towards people and culture and is related to organizational change and development in the areas of commitment and leadership, customer relations and human resource management. In addition, Yazdani et al., (2016) also defines infrastructure quality as a

condition of quality improvement that focuses on organizational change and development in the areas of commitment and leadership, management, and human resource management.

The focus of infrastructure quality is the behavior of members of the organization and also the application of the values held by members of the organization. Quality management is able to maintain the continuity of the quality of an organization in providing services and also producing products according to the wishes of its customers. The role of quality infrastructure is to maintain that the behavior of existing human resources is always quality-oriented. Addis (2020) reveals that infrastructure quality (soft) is a quality improvement method that includes a higher dimension of human resource management at the organizational level and is oriented towards people and culture.

Core Quality

In addition to the human resource and cultural approach to the quality management aspect of continuous quality improvement within the organization, there is a core quality aspect that focuses on the techniques and methods of implementing quality improvement. In quality management, core quality plays an important role where the source of information and the management of product and service design is one aspect that can support the sustainability of the organization. Zeng et al (2017) define core quality (hard) as a quality management practice that focuses on controlling processes and products through techniques and tools to meet established requirements. Meanwhile, Flynn et al., (1995) revealed that core quality includes techniques and methodologies that are expected to lead directly to increased performance. Core practices in quality management typically include quality information, process control, and product design management (Saraph et al., 1989; Anderson et al., 1995). The point is continual improvement, where “fact-based management” relies on data and information gathered from multiple sources and applied to statistical process control (Snell and Hui, 2000).

Service Quality

The concept of perceived service quality was first introduced by Grönroos (1984). According to him, perceived service quality is a process of evaluating consumer's assessment of service excellence as a whole through a comparison of the expected service with the perceived service. Meanwhile, according to Zeithaml et al (1990) Perceived service quality is the result of a comparison of customer service expectations with actual service perceptions and is used as a global consideration. The customer's perception of service value is not necessarily the same as the organization's perception of service quality, so perceptions of service quality change over time.

Service quality is defined as the difference between customer expectations for service performance prior to service encounters and their perceived service perception” (Asubonteng, McCleary and Swan, 1996). The core concept of service quality is disconfirmation of expectations theory (Dawes and Rowley, 1999). According to disconfirmation of expectations theory, comparison of expectations and perceptions of service will result in a disconfirmation decision (Ruyter, Bloemer and Peeters, 1997) and subsequently this

disconfirmation will affect the perceived service quality (Gotlieb, Grewal and Brown, 1994; Philip and Hazlett, 1997).

Customers form positive disconfirmations when the performance of the service offered by the service provider exceeds their previous expectations whereas, customers will form negative disconfirmations when the previous expectations exceed the performance of the services offered by the service provider (Ruyter, et. al., 1997). make an impact k is negative on the perceived quality of the services offered (Gotlieb, et. al., 1994).

Satisfaction

Satisfaction will arise if the needs and desires of consumers can be met by quality goods or services. Whether or not consumers are satisfied with an item or service is determined by the behavior that appears after using the item or service. Zeithaml et al, (2009) define satisfaction as a consumer's assessment of the features of a product or service, or the product or service itself, providing a level of consumer satisfaction with their consumption. Hunt (1977) defines satisfaction as a consumer's overall assessment of using a service or product experience. Satisfaction is considered as what a person gains from performance experience and the extent to which his needs are met

Gerson (1993) suggests that the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction is determined by customer perceptions. Satisfaction is the customer's perception that expectations have been met. Therefore, if the academic service is good then customer satisfaction will follow. Lovelock & Wright (2002) suggest that a high level of customer satisfaction is a policy guarantee to overcome an error. Long-term customers are usually more forgiving in these situations, because bad experiences are replaced by previous positive experiences, and satisfied customers are less likely to be influenced by competitors' offerings. Student satisfaction is a concept that can be defined in different ways. For example, a short-term approach that results from a student's educational experience (or a student's mental assessment of the outcomes and experiences of education and school life can be considered as a student's level of satisfaction (Elliott and Shin 2002).Browne et al.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH METHODS

Conceptual Framework

The following conceptual framework in this study as a reference in developing the latent construct is as follows:

Information :

<p>Quality Culture (X)</p> <p>X1.1 = Discipline culture</p> <p>X1.2 = Culture of self-development</p> <p>X1.3 = Preparation, implementation and assessment of the learning process</p> <p>X1.4 = Provision of learning facilities for students</p> <p>X1.5 = Quality improvement-oriented budget management</p> <p>Source: Madrasah Self Evaluation Guidelines (EDM) Ministry of Religion (2021)</p> <p>Core quality (Y2)</p> <p>Y2.1 = Quality of information and communication</p>	<p>Infrastructure Quality (Y1)</p> <p>Y1.1 = Commitment of leadership and management</p> <p>Y1.2 = Training</p> <p>Y1.3 = Internal client commitment and involvement</p> <p>Y1.4 = External client commitment and involvement</p> <p>Source: Garcia and Lorente (2019)</p> <p>Service Quality (Y3)</p> <p>Y3.1 = Real proof</p> <p>Y3.2 = Teaching</p> <p>Y3.3 = Facilitative services</p> <p>Y3.4 = Support service</p>
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<p>Y2.2 = Education service</p> <p>Y2.3 = Process management</p> <p>Source: Garcia and Lorente (2019)</p>	<p>Y3.5 = School organization</p> <p>Source: Garcia and Lorente (2019)</p> <p>Satisfaction (Y4)</p> <p>Y4.1 = Pleasure</p> <p>Y4.2 = Sharing positive information</p> <p>Y4.3 = No complaints</p> <p>Source: Garbarino and Johnson (1999)</p>
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Hypothesis

the research hypothesis is a provisional assumption regarding the relationship between two or more variables. The research hypotheses proposed in this study are:

1. Quality culture has a positive and significant impact on infrastructure quality
2. Quality culture has a positive and significant effect on core quality
3. Quality culture has a positive and significant effect on service quality
4. Quality culture has a positive and significant effect on satisfaction
5. Infrastructure quality has a positive and significant impact on core quality
6. Infrastructure quality has a positive and significant impact on service quality
7. Core quality has a positive and significant effect on service quality
8. Service quality has a positive and significant effect on satisfaction
9. Infrastructure quality significantly mediates the influence of quality culture on core quality
10. Core quality significantly mediates the effect of infrastructure quality on service quality

RESEARCH METHODS

This research design uses a positivist paradigm with the type of explanatory research in which data collection is carried out in a cross-sectional manner. Explanatory research is intended to provide an explanation of the causal effect between variables through hypothesis testing or aims to obtain appropriate testing in drawing causality (causal) conclusions between variables and subsequently having alternative actions (Cooper & Schindler, 2003).

The population in this study were all students at the Madrasah Tsanawiyah level at the Ummusshabri Foundation, Kendari City, totaling 576 students. To determine the sample in this study by considering the students' ability to feel the quality culture, infrastructure quality, core quality, service quality and satisfaction provided by Madrasah Tsanawiyah, and their ability to answer well regarding research instruments, the sample of this study was determined only for grade IX students. with a total of 206 people, taking into account the respondent's stability in feeling related to what is being studied.

Data analysis in this study will be carried out using Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis which is an approach using a path diagram that allows to include all observer variables according to the related theoretical model. PLS is a statistical technique that allows the simultaneous testing of a series of fairly complex relationships.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Quality culture has a positive and significant impact on infrastructure quality
The results of the quality culture test on the quality of infrastructure are obtained by the estimated path coefficient value of 0.256 with a positive direction. The positive path coefficient means that the influence between quality culture and infrastructure quality is unidirectional. The significance result is evidenced by the -value of $0.015 < = 0.05$ which is interpreted as a significant influence. Based on this, it can be explained that the quality culture has a positive and significant effect on the quality of infrastructure.
2. Quality culture has a positive and significant effect on core quality
The results of the quality culture test on core quality obtained an estimate path coefficient value of 0.430 with a positive direction. The positive path coefficient means that the influence between quality culture and core quality is unidirectional. The significance result is evidenced by the -value of $0.000 < = 0.05$ which is interpreted as a significant influence. Based on this, it can be concluded that quality culture has a positive and significant effect on core quality.
3. Quality culture has a positive and significant effect on service quality
The results of the quality culture test on service quality obtained the estimated path coefficient value of 0.775 with a positive direction. The positive path coefficient means that the influence between quality culture and service quality is unidirectional. The significance result is evidenced by the -value of $0.000 < = 0.05$ which is interpreted as a significant influence. Based on this, it can be concluded that quality culture has a positive and significant effect on service quality.
4. Quality culture has a positive and significant effect on satisfaction
The results of the quality culture test on satisfaction obtained a path coefficient estimate value of 0.765 with a positive direction. The positive path coefficient means that the influence between quality culture and satisfaction is unidirectional. The significance result is evidenced by the -value of $0.000 < = 0.05$ which is interpreted as a significant influence. Based on this, it can be concluded that the quality culture has a positive and significant effect on satisfaction.
5. Infrastructure quality has a positive and significant impact on core quality
The results of testing the quality of infrastructure against the quality of the core obtained a path coefficient estimate value of 0.035 with a positive direction. The positive path coefficient means that the influence between infrastructure quality and core quality is unidirectional. The results are not significant as evidenced by the -value of $0.331 > = 0.05$ which is interpreted as an insignificant effect. Based on this, it can be explained that the quality of infrastructure has a positive and significant effect on core quality.
6. Infrastructure quality has a positive and significant impact on service quality

The results of testing the quality of infrastructure on service quality are obtained by the estimated path coefficient value of 0.782 with a positive direction. The positive path coefficient means that the influence between infrastructure quality and service quality is unidirectional. The significance result is evidenced by the -value of $0.000 < = 0.05$ which is interpreted as a significant influence. Based on this, it can be concluded that the quality of infrastructure has a positive and significant effect on service quality.

7. Core quality has a positive and significant effect on service quality

The results of testing the core quality of service quality obtained the estimated path coefficient value of 0.440 in a positive direction. The positive path coefficient means that the influence between core quality and service quality is unidirectional. The significance result is evidenced by the -value of $0.000 < = 0.05$ which is interpreted as a significant influence. Based on this, it can be concluded that core quality has a positive and significant effect on service quality.

8. Service quality has a positive and significant effect on satisfaction

The results of the service quality test on satisfaction obtained the estimated path coefficient value of 0.350 with a positive direction. The path coefficient is positive, which means that the influence between service quality and satisfaction is unidirectional. The significance result is evidenced by the -value of $0.000 < = 0.05$ which is interpreted as a significant influence. Based on this, it can be concluded that service quality has a positive and significant effect on satisfaction.

9. Infrastructure quality significantly mediates the influence of quality culture on core quality

Based on the formula using z-statistics, the mediating effect of the infrastructure quality variable in bridging the influence of quality culture on core quality is based on the path coefficient value, then based on the calculation results, the z-value is 3.664, because the z-value obtained is $1.664 < 1.96$ with a significance level of 5 % then proves that the quality of infrastructure is not able to mediate the influence of quality culture on core quality.

10. Core quality significantly mediates the effect of infrastructure quality on service quality

Based on the formula for using z-statistics, the mediating effect of the core quality variable in bridging the influence of infrastructure quality on service quality is based on the path coefficient value, then based on the calculation results, the z-value is 3.863, because the z-value obtained is $3.863 > 1.96$ with a significance level of 5 % then proves that core quality is able to mediate the influence of infrastructure quality on service quality.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this study is that quality culture, core quality, service quality, satisfaction have a positive and significant effect on infrastructure quality. Infrastructure quality has a positive and significant effect on core quality and service quality, then core quality has a positive and significant effect on service quality, service quality has a positive effect on student satisfaction at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Ummushabri Kendari. Then the mediating role of infrastructure quality is not able to mediate quality culture on core quality, while core

quality is able to mediate on the influence of infrastructure quality on service quality at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Ummusshabri Kendari.

FURTHER RESEARCH SUGGESTIONS

In this study, observations were made using cross-sectional time coverage, which means that data was obtained from a certain time or only behavior at the time of the study, while the behavior or answers of respondents at other times (time series) and certain conditions were not covered in this study. In addition, this research uses quantitative methods using questionnaires so that the same question will be in different conditions when asked at different times and conditions of the fabric, therefore it is highly recommended to conduct further research by raising the variables of motivation, spiritualism and belief.

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